

RM ROADMAP

D5.1: Quality Management Plan (QMP)

This document defines the common management and project procedures in RM Roadmap as common standards to assist in the implementation and management of the project.

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

Project full title

“Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area”

Project acronym

RM Roadmap

Grant Agreement no.

101058475

D5.1: Quality Management Plan

Authors:	Borana Taraj, Nik Claesen
Reviewer(s):	David Langley, Laura Macdonald, Kristof Vlaeminck, Cristina Oliveira, Virág Zsár, Michael Papadopoulos, Anja Gilis
Dissemination level ¹ :	PU
Submission date:	28-02-2023
Start date of project:	September 1st , 2022
Duration of the project:	36 months
Organisation name of lead contractor for this deliverable:	EARMA

Copyright by RM Roadmap consortium

¹This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreementNo 101058475

PU – Public (fully open, automatically posted online on the Project Result platforms);SE – Sensitive (limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement);

CO – EU classified: EU restricted, EU confidential, EU secret under Decision 2015/444.

Document metadata

Version	Date	Modification reason	Modified by
1.0	21-02-2023	First draft	Borana Taraj, Nik Claesen
2.0	28-02-2023	Second draft	David Langley, Laura Macdonald, Kristof Vlaeminck, Cristina Oliveira, Virág Zsár, Michael Papadopoulos, Anja Gilis

Table of Contents

1. SUMMARY	5
2. INTRODUCTION RM ROADMAP	6
2.1. Background.....	6
2.2. Project ID Card.....	7
2.3. Project Objectives	9
3. WORK PACKAGES, MILESTONES AND DELIVERABLES	11
3.2 Work packages	11
3.3 Milestones	14
3.4 Deliverables	16
3.4.1 Deliverables submission process and quality review	18
4. PROJECT ORGANISATION & STRUCTURE.....	25
4.1 Management structure	25
4.2 Project Organisation (by time)	27
4.3 Task Control and Monitoring.....	29
3 COMMUNICATION.....	31
7.1. Internal communication within the consortium	31
7.2. External communication	31
7.3. Complaints and conflict resolution	31
4 MEETINGS.....	32
5 RESOURCE PLANNING	34

1. SUMMARY

This document defines the common management and project procedures in RM Roadmap. It is built in a handbook style with practical information that does not appear in the Grant Agreement (GA) and complements information from the GA.

This document specifies, where applicable - exact dates, links to or annexes of satellite documents and systems, that were agreed in the GA and are considered necessary or a common standard to assist in the implementation and management of the project. In case of contradiction between the GA and Consortium Agreement (CA) and this deliverable - the GA and CA always precede.

The guidelines presented here will be monitored during the project's lifetime and updated, if needed.

The main objectives of this deliverable are to:

- ensure smooth implementation and timely completion of the project activities;
- guarantee the quality of the activities and deliverables of the project in line with the contractual obligations enclosed in the Grant Agreement and in compliance with the Consortium Agreement signed by all RM Roadmap beneficiaries.

To this end, the QMP provides an overview of the management structure, describes the responsibilities of the partners, defines the procedures for ensuring the quality of project deliverables and for communication within and outside the consortium as well as presents procedures for progress monitoring and reporting.

Compliance with the QMP is obligatory for all project partners. The QMP complements and does not replace the Grant Agreement signed with the EC, its Annexes, and the Consortium Agreement of the project.

2. INTRODUCTION RM ROADMAP

2.1. Background

RM Roadmap will chart a course for the future of research management (RM) in Europe and a community to support its delivery. It will be conducted over 36 months and is funded to the amount of €1.5m by the European Commission Horizon Europe funding programme.

The overarching objective of RM Roadmap is to identify and adapt the research management capital base of the EU, including the widening countries, and emerging needs of its current and future research management workforce to improve the EU's competitiveness and sustain its economic performance.

RM Roadmap will allow existing European networks to connect on a smart community platform which will enable an unprecedented consultation process in research management. This co-creation process will gather the existing communities and expand upon them to reach two main objectives: to create and inform a bottom-up consensus on the future of RM in a roadmap, and to inform the community about existing training, networking, funding, and career mobility opportunities.

Eight partners are working together on this project: European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (Belgium); HETFA Research Institute (Hungary); Nova University Lisbon (Portugal); Association of European Science & Technology Transfer Professionals (Netherlands); Crowdhelix Limited (Ireland), The Cyprus Institute (Cyprus) and associated partners Janssen Pharmaceuticals (J&J) and Una Europa (Belgium).

2.2. Project ID Card

Project Name	RM Roadmap «Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area»
Contracting parties / Beneficiaries	<p>The European Commission and the following principal contractors:</p> <p>RM ROADMAP consists of 8 partners:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. [EUROPEAN ASSOCIATION OF RESEARCH MANAGERS AND ADMINISTRATORS], Belgium (the Coordinator) 2. [HETFA KUTATOINTEZET KFT - HETFA RESEARCH INSTITUTE LTD], [HETFA], Hungary (Beneficiary) 3. [UNIVERSIDADE NOVA DE LISBOA], [UNL], Portugal (Beneficiary) 4. [ASSOCIATION OF EUROPEAN SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER PROFESSIONALS], [ASTP], Netherlands (Beneficiary) 5. [CROWDHELIX LIMITED], [CROWDHELIX], Ireland (Beneficiary) 6. [THE CYPRUS INSTITUTE], [CYI], Cyprus (Beneficiary) 7. [JANSSEN PHARMACEUTICA NV], [J&J], Belgium (Associated Partner) 8. [Una Europa vzw], [UNAE], Belgium (Associated Partner)

RM Roadmap_EARMA_WP5_D5.1_Quality Management Plan Management

Project type	CSA Coordination and Support Action
Project ID	101058475
Project start date	September 1st, 2022
Project end date	August 31, 2025
Total duration	36 months
Total effort	192
Budget (total costs)	1 499 997.00 EUR
Maximum EU contribution	1 499 997.00 EUR (funding rate = 100%)

Table N.1: Project Identification

European Commission (EC), CORDIS EU research results:

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101058475>

All Principal Investigators (PIs) and partner admin have access to the EC portal and they can manage/control project access credentials directly.

2.3. Project Objectives

The overarching objective of RM ROADMAP is to identify and adapt the research management capital base of the EU, including the widening countries, and emerging needs of its current and future research management workforce to improve EU's competitiveness and sustain its economic performance.

The project will connect existing European networks on a smart community platform which will enable an unprecedented co-creation process in research management in the world. This co-creation process will gather the existing communities and expand upon them to reach two main objectives - To create and inform a bottom-up consensus on the future of RM in a roadmap, and to inform the community about existing training, networking, funding, and mobility opportunities.

See below graphics with RM Roadmap objectives.

RM ROADMAP Objectives

Connect new and existing European networks on a community platform to:

1. create a bottom-up consensus about the future of RM
2. inform about the existing training, networking, funding and mobility opportunities.

Clarify the role and potential for Research Managers to support the ERA and overall R&I System:

- Efficiency & Effectiveness
- Quality Control
- Reducing administrative burden for researchers
- Trust and accountability

Figure 1 RM Roadmap objectives

Figure 2 RM Roadmap objectives

3. WORK PACKAGES, MILESTONES AND DELIVERABLES

3.2 Work packages

The following table contains the project's work packages, with dates:

WP	Title	Lead Beneficiary	WP leader name	Person months	Start month	Start date	End month	End date
1	Intelligence	HETFA	Virág Zsár	41	1	1 Sept. 2022	36	31 Aug. 2025
2	Training and Development	NOVA	Cristina Oliveira	43	1	1 Sept. 2022	36	31 Aug. 2025
3	Roadmap and Advocacy	EARMA	Nik Claesen	24	1	1 Sept. 2022	36	31 Aug. 2025
4	Community, Communication and Dissemination	CHX	David Langley	50	1	1 Sept. 2022	36	31 Aug. 2025
5	Project Management	EARMA	Nik Claesen	14	1	1 Sept. 2022	36	31 Aug. 2025
6	Sustainability and Exploitation	ASTP	Laura Macdonald	20	3	1 Dec. 2022	36	31 Aug. 2025

Table N. 2 List of Work packages

RM Roadmap_EARMA_WP5_D5.1_Quality Management Plan Management

The following table provides contact partner information.

Partner	Contact person	Contact details
HETFA	Virág Zsár	zsarvirag@hetfa.hu rm-roadmap@hetfa.hu
NOVA	Cristina Oliveira	coliveira@novaims.unl.pt
EARMA	Nik Claesen Borana Taraj Olaf Svenningsen	Nik.claesen@earma.org Borana.taraj@earma.org Olaf.Svenningsen@earma.org
CHX	David Langley	david.langley@crowdhelix.com
CYI	Michalis Yiangou Andri Charalambous Marina Papageorgiou Michael Papadopoulos	vpo@cyi.ac.cy m.papadopoulos@cyi.ac.cy a.charalambous@cyi.ac.cy m.papageorgiou@cyi.ac.cy
ASTP	Laura Macdonald	laura.macdonald@astp4kt.eu
J&J	Anja Gilis	agilis@its.jnj.com
UNAE	Kristof Vlaeminck Emily Palmer	kristof.vlaeminck@una-europa.eu emily.palmer@una-europa.eu

Table N. 3: Contact partner information

The below figure provides an illustration of the interconnection between the different WPs.

Figure N. 3 Interconnection between the RM Roadmap WPs

3.3 Milestones

The following table contains the project's milestones, with dates:

Milestone Nr	Name	WP N.	Lead Beneficiary	Means	Due date	Actual date
1	Website launched	WP4	CHX	Website launched	M4	31 December 2022
2	Knowledge and Community Platform online*	WP4	EARMA	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype	M6	28 February 2023
3	Recruitment of Ambassadors and Communities of Practice Moderators	WP1	EARMA	Report published on the project website	M9	31 May 2023
4	Roadmap Plan	WP3	EARMA	D3.3 Short policy brief 1	M12	31 August 2023
5	Online tool on professional development opportunities*	WP1, WP2	NOVA	D2.2	M24	31 August 2024
6	Data management Plan reviewed and updated	WP5	EARMA	Revised plan online	M34	30 June 2025
7	ERA wide landscape	WP1	HETFA	Report on ERA-wide landscape	M36	31 August 2025
8	Online member confirmation data	WP4	CHX	150 members enrolled under the Research Management Helix	M36	31 August 2025
9	Overarching Roadmap	WP3	EARMA	Report published online	M36	31 August 2025

Table N. 4 Project milestones

The following information constitutes minor deviations from the GA in terms of milestones:

- * Recruitment of Ambassadors and Communities of Practice Moderators (Report published on the project website by 31 May 2023):
 - The project consortium has focused its attention on the recruitment of national ambassadors to be completed by the end of May 2023. The recruitment of the Communities of Practice Moderators will be completed by January 2024. The reason is that the subcategories of communities of practice need to be defined in WP1 also in close collaboration with the [CARDEA Horizon Europe project](#) "Career Acknowledgement for Research (Managers) Delivering for the European Area". In total, eight ambassador sessions are planned (physical or online). More information about the recruitment of the ambassadors is available on the project website: <https://www.rmroadmap.eu/faqs>
- * RM Roadmap is working in close collaboration with the CARDEA project for D2.2. Based on preliminary discussions, there will be only one online tool repository for training, networking, mobility and funding opportunities for research managers so that there is a clear understanding of where to find reliable and complete information. RM ROADMAP will complete desk-based research on training, networking, mobility and funding opportunities. RM ROADMAP will provide this information for inclusion on CARDEA's online dashboard. Both coordinators share this willingness to collaborate for the good of the RM community and the R&I system where synergies exist.

3.4 Deliverables

The below table provides the list of RM Roadmap deliverables

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	WP number	Lead beneficiary	Type	Dissemination	Due Date (M)	Due Date (Actual month)
D1.1	Preliminary report on ERA-wide landscape	WP1	HETFA	R	PU	M12	August 2023
D1.2	Report on ERA-wide landscape	WP1	HETFA	R	PU	M34	June 2025
D2.1	Preliminary report on professional development opportunities	WP2	NOVA	DEC	PU	M12	August 2023
D2.2	Online tool for professional development opportunities	WP2	NOVA	R	PU	M24	August 2024
D2.3	Report on the professional development opportunities	WP2	NOVA	R	PU	M34	June 2025
D3.1	Short policy brief 1	WP3	EARMA	R	PU	M12	August 2023
D3.2	Overarching Roadmap Plan	WP3	EARMA	R	PU	M12	August 2023
D3.3	Short policy brief 2	WP3	EARMA	R	PU	M36	August 2025
D3.4	Overarching roadmap	WP3	EARMA	R	PU	M36	August 2025
D4.1	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DCE) Plan	WP4	CHX	R	PU	M6	February 2023
D4.2	Online Knowledge	WP4	EARMA	DEM	PU	M6	February

RM Roadmap_EARMA_WP5_D5.1_Quality Management Plan Management

	and Community Platform (KCP)						2023
D4.3	Activity report on KCP and DCE	WP4	EARMA	R	PU	12	August 2023
D4.4	Preliminary Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation report	WP4	CHX	R	PU	12	August 2023
D4.5	Activity Report on Knowledge and Community Platform	WP4	EARMA	R	PU	34	June 2025
D4.6	Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation report	WP4	CHX	R	PU	34	June 2025
D5.1	Quality Management Plan	WP5	EARMA	R	PU	6	February 2023
D5.2	Data Management Plan	WP5	EARMA	R	PU	6	February 2023
D5.3	First Management and Coordination report	WP5	EARMA	R	PU	12	August 2023
D5.4	Final Management and Coordination report	WP5	EARMA	R	PU	36	August 2025
D6.1	Sustainability Plan	WP6	ASTP	R	PU	12	August 2023
D6.2	Final sustainability report	WP6	ASTP	R	PU	34	June 2025

Table N. 5 RM Roadmap deliverables

3.4.1 Deliverables submission process and quality review

EARMA has designed a deliverables' review process to enhance the quality of RM Roadmap deliverables, as well as to support information and collaboration within the project. Reviewers are encouraged to provide constructive comments and realistically feasible suggestions that focus on improving the quality of the deliverables. Participation in the review process is voluntary, but strongly encouraged.

Reviewers are project partners or Advisory Board members (AB) who can provide critical review based on their own experience, knowledge, expertise etc.

Process

- *Three weeks in advance of the deadline:* Each Lead Beneficiary sends the report to the assigned reviewers (partner and/or AB). Reviewers have one week to send back their comments to the lead beneficiary.
- *Two weeks in advance of the deadline:* The lead beneficiary has one week to address the comments and send the final version to EARMA for review.
- *One week in advance of the deadline:* EARMA has one week to review the report before it is submitted on time to the European Commission through the dedicated portal.

EARMA has also created a common template to be used for all RM Roadmap project deliverables. The sample document exemplifies the layout and typographical features of the cover page, executive summary page, header, footer and heading levels to be employed in a typical document to all consortium members in MS-Word format attributed "RM Roadmap deliverables template" in the shared EMDESK electronic spaces (see section 4.3).

All the graphics materials were developed by EARMA. EARMA developed the project's Logo, as well as the presentation (powerpoint) and word document templates which use a graphical logo designed specifically for the RM Roadmap project (examples shown below).

Template for RM Roadmap deliverables (1/2)

Please enter your title here

Please enter your text here

Please enter your text here

RM Roadmap **EARMA_WP5_D5.2_Data Management Plan**

Project full title

“Creating Framework Conditions for Research Management to Strengthen the European Research Area”

Project acronym

RM Roadmap

Grant Agreement no.

101058475

D5.2: Data Management Plan

1

Template for RM Roadmap deliverables (2/2)

RM ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.

RM Roadmap_EARMA_WP5_D5.2_Data Management Plan

Insert table of contents here

1. Contents

1. SUMMARY	4
2. INTRODUCTION	4
3. BACKGROUND	4

Insert Headlines (example below)

1. Summary
2. Introduction
 - 2.1. RM Roadmap

RM Roadmap will chart a course for the future of research management (RM) in Europe and a community to support its delivery. It will be conducted over 36 months and is funded to the amount of €1.5m by the European Commission Horizon Europe funding programme.
The overarching objective of RM Roadmap is to identify and adapt the research management capital base of the EU, including the widening countries, and emerging needs of its current and future research management workforce to improve the EU's competitiveness and sustain its economic performance.
RM Roadmap will allow existing European networks to connect on a smart community platform which will enable an unprecedented consultation process in research management. This co-creation process will gather the existing communities and expand upon them to reach two main objectives: to create and inform a bottom-up consensus on the future of RM in a roadmap, and to inform the community about existing training, networking, funding, and career mobility opportunities.
Eight partners are working together on this project: European Association of Research Managers and Administrators (Belgium), HETFA Research Institute (Hungary), Nova University Lisbon (Portugal), Association of European Science & Technology Transfer Professionals (Netherlands), CrossRx Limited (Ireland), The Cyprus Institute (Cyprus) and associated partners Janssen Pharmaceuticals (J&J) and Una Europa (Belgium).
[Adapt if necessary]

3. Background

rmroadmap.eu

[@rmroadmap](https://twitter.com/rmroadmap)

[linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap](https://www.linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap)

RM Roadmap_EARMA_WP5_D5.1_Quality Management Plan Management

Project logo

The project identity has been developed, including a logo (se below).

A set of slides using this identity is provided that can be used without further additional permission and will be maintained and updated as RM-ROADMAP progresses.

RM Roadmap_EARMA_WP5_D5.1_Quality Management Plan Management

RM Roadmap Powerpoint template

Click to add title

- Click to add text

RM Roadmap Letterhead (concept design)

For official letters written in the name of the consortium, a letterhead of the project is created. It is in the format of MS-Word available on the shared electronic spaces.

4. PROJECT ORGANISATION & STRUCTURE

4.1 Management structure

RM Roadmap features the following management structure, adequate to handle a collaborative project.

- **The Coordinator (EARMA)** – is responsible for the financial, administrative, and operative coordination between the Work Packages, contingency planning, and crisis management, as well as for the facilitation of internal communication within the project and will interface on all matters with the European Commission. Specifically, the Coordinator is responsible for the day-to-day supervision and monitoring of project activities in line with the pre-defined timetable, ensuring fulfilment of all contractual requirements, coordination of activities between partners, organisation of project meetings, ensuring high quality of produced outputs, technical and financial reporting, including regular monitoring of project costs, follow up on EC payments, assistance to beneficiaries on specific administrative and financial issues, and carrying out periodic financial monitoring.

General Assembly (GA) – comprises all Beneficiaries, is chaired by the Coordinator, and will convene at least once per calendar year. At this annual meeting, all the Beneficiaries will have the possibility to be informed about the progress of the project, discuss project results, and make strategic decisions, where needed. The Coordinator will compile the agendas, send the invitations and write and distribute the meeting minutes. The roles and responsibilities of each partner are described in detail within Annex 1 to the Grant Agreement. All partners should take the necessary measures and provide all necessary resources for the on-time and smooth elaboration of their tasks and responsibilities.

- **Technical Support Committee (Executive Meetings)** – is composed of Work Package and Task leaders (one representative per partner) and is chaired by the Coordinator. The committee will support the Coordinator in managing the project and its core functions will be the following: i) Ensuring coordination of the Work Package activities, ii) Assisting Beneficiaries in performing their respective activities within the Work Packages, iii) Taking executive decisions regarding the development of activities in the project. To ensure effective coordination of all project activities, the executive committee will meet virtually about every two months during the full lifetime of the project. The Coordinator will compile the agendas, send the invitations and write and distribute the meeting minutes. During the executive meetings, each WP or task leader provides an update for the most recent developments and shares key plans for the months that follow in its area of responsibility.
- **Advisory Board (AB)** – has the purpose to provide independent, effective, and evolving support to the RM Roadmap project over its life cycle. The AB will provide independent observations and assessment of the RM Roadmap project strategies and performance at milestones in the project life. The AB will engage and provide guidance on specific project issues escalated for its visibility and potential action by the RM

RM Roadmap_EARMA_WP5_D5.1_Quality Management Plan Management

Roadmap Coordinator, project staff, Partners and WP Leads. The AB will be invited to provide feedback on core project-related elements, including project deliverables and work packages based on their expertise, e.g. assessment of methodology, comments on quality, inconsistencies, identification of gaps etc.

Advisory Board members include:

- Ana Marusic, Professor, University of Split School of Medicine
- Jan Andersen, Chief Executive Advisor at the Technical University of Denmark
- Karl Kerschbaum, Vice Director, Regional Network Coordinator at Euresearch
- Kathleen Larmett, Executive Director at National Council of University Research Administrators (NCURA)
- Kurt Deketelaere, Secretary-General of the League of European Research Universities (LERU)
- Thomas Estermann, Director for Governance, Funding and Public Policy Development at the European University Association
- Eduard Balbuena Longo, Professor, Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona/ICERCA - Research Centres of Catalonia/CARDEA Horizon Europe project

Following the Consortium meeting of 25 January 2023, CARDEA will have an Advisory Board (AB) member represented in RM Roadmap and vice versa RM Roadmap will be represented on CARDEA AB to ensure that opportunities for collaboration are well captured.

Eduard Balbuena Longo is CARDEA representative within RM Roadmap Advisory Board.

Olaf Svenningsen, Senior Project Advisor (EARMA) is RM Roadmap representative within CARDEA Advisory Board.

The below figures exemplify the overall project management structure.

Figure 4. Project management structure (1s September 2022)

Note: The picture includes Advisory Board members as of 1 September 2022. The list is not exhaustive.

New AB member added on 25/01/2023: Eduard Balbuena Longo.

Other AB members could be added by the project's General Assembly.

4.2 Project Organisation (by time)

The project is presented in calendric sequence. The project timeline is composed from work packages (& tasks), deliverables, milestones and meetings.

The project workplan can be found below and is also available on the project management platform EMDESK.

RM Roadmap_EARMA_WP5_D5.1_Quality Management Plan Management

Figure N.5. Project timeline

4.3 Task Control and Monitoring

After a three week of trial period, the consortium decided to work with the project management and internal communication tool, called EMDESK.

EMDESK is a single project and financial management platform that unifies planning, controlling, execution, and collaboration in projects. It helps teams and stakeholders to work together, while maintaining maximum control and transparency. EMDESK guarantees the highest security standards. EMDESK is headquartered in Germany. The production systems and customer data is stored in secure data centres with Open Telekom Cloud (OTC) in Germany.

EMDESK will be kept as the main tool for communication among consortium partners. Using EMDESK enables new members that join throughout the duration, to go back in time and review the communication, files etc, without needing to dig in large amount of emails.

RM Roadmap has a EMDESK license of 15 users and unlimited guests. Users can manage (create new records, update, move and delete records), edit (update records) and read (read records). Guests can read records. Each partner has at least one or two user rights and unlimited guest rights. The owner of the platform is the coordinator, EARMA and the cost (roughly 82eur per month) is covered from the project budget.

EMDESK has a variety of project planning, reporting and controlling as well as free resources about Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects. A screenshot of RM Roadmap project collaboration space on EMDESK is provided below.

RM Roadmap_EARMA_WP5_D5.1_Quality Management Plan Management

Figure N.6. Project monitoring on EMDESK project management platform

The Project website <https://www.rmroadmap.eu/> will remain as means to communicate with all other stakeholders that are exterior to the consortium. As such, all publicly available deliverables of the project, as defined in the GA, will be available through the website.

3 COMMUNICATION

7.1. Internal communication within the consortium

The Coordinator has the main responsibility of ensuring smooth and effective internal communication. Communication between Beneficiaries will primarily take place through online communication means, namely emails and online calls and meetings.

7.2. External communication

- Communication with the EC

The Coordinator (EARMA) is the sole responsible for the communication with the Project Officer (PO) with respect to the project. Project partners should not contact the PO without previous discussion with EARMA. Only in exceptional cases, and if the PO requires so, may a project partner directly contact the PO. In such a case the Coordinator shall be kept fully informed (in writing) about the content of the communication.

The Coordinator has the responsibility of submitting to the EC all reports and deliverables of the project. They also provide the EC with any additional information and/or clarification that have been requested by the EC services. Finally, the Coordinator will keep all Beneficiaries informed about any important communication with the EC.

- Communication with third parties

Project partners may and should communicate with third parties (e.g. national authorities, local stakeholders, other EU-funded projects) within the context of the project. In all external communications, a reference to the project should be made (e.g. project acronym, EU programme, GA No).

7.3. Complaints and conflict resolution

Each WP leader will immediately notify the Coordinator about any event or circumstance that may significantly affect the performance of the work executed in the frame of their work package (e.g. suggestions for considerable improvements and modifications/changes in the methodology, timetable, and task allocation, potential delays, disputes between partners, etc.). The Coordinator will be responsible for and will take the necessary steps to resolve the abovementioned issues by consulting with the relevant WP leaders and any partner directly involved in the respective Work Package.

Further details with respect to decision-making, conflict resolution as well as the management of internal administrative and financial issues are incorporated in the project's Consortium Agreement.

4 MEETINGS

Physical meetings are considered as crucial to maintain good working relationships. However, the number of planned physical meetings in RM Roadmap will be limited due to the limited resources available and to take into account environmental challenges.

For coordination purposes at the level of the consortium, in addition to the General Assembly meetings and Ambassador network meetings, the coordinator (EARMA) has planned informal online partners' meetings. The purpose is to keep the number of the meetings to a reasonable number and find a balance between coordination and independent work for each work package.

Furthermore, a regular dialogue is established between the RM Roadmap coordinators (EARMA) and the CARDEA coordinators (University College Cork), as well as partners from each of the two projects working on areas of common collaboration (HETFFA, NOVA from RM Roadmap and University of Macerata, CERCA from CARDEA). Cross-coordination from both projects occurs through joint meetings every six/eight weeks.

The following meetings are foreseen in RM Roadmap with the full consortium partners:

Date	Online/physical	Lead partner	Meeting	Type
2022, September 8th	Belgrade/online	EARMA	Broadcast RM Roadmap 1st General Assembly/Official Kick-off meeting	Broadcast/official launch / General Assembly
2023, January 25th	Online	EARMA	Consortium meeting: Update from coordinator and open discussion with partners	Informal
2023, May, 8-10th	Budapest	EARMA/HETFFA	General Assembly/Ambassador Meeting Back-to-back with ERA Action 17 Workshop	General Assembly/Ambassador meeting

RM Roadmap_EARMA_WP5_D5.1_Quality Management Plan Management

2023, September 20th	Online	EARMA	Consortium meeting: Update from coordinator and open discussion with partners	Informal
2024, January 24th	Online	EARMA	General Assembly	General Assembly
2024, March 13th	Lisbon	NOVA	Ambassadors meeting	Ambassadors meeting
2024, June 12th	Online	EARMA	Consortium meeting: Update from coordinator and open discussion with partners	Informal
2024, November, 12-13th	Brussels/Online	EARMA	Short General Assembly & Ambassador Meeting	General Assembly/Ambassador meeting
2025, March, 19th	Cyprus	EARMA/CYI	General Assembly	General Assembly
2025, June 11th	Online or physical (tbc)	EARMA	Brussels stakeholders dissemination meeting, Online dissemination conference	Dissemination event

Table N. 6 RM Roadmap meetings

5 RESOURCE PLANNING

The following table presents the resource planning of the project.

Participant	WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6	Total Person-Months
1 - EARMA	4.00	4.00	9.00	12.00	9.00	6.00	44.00
2 - HETFA	25.00	7.00	3.00	8.00	1.00		44.00
3 - NOVA	5.00	24.00		10.00	1.00		40.00
4 - ASTP	7.00	2.00	6.00	3.00	1.00	8.00	27.00
5 - CHX		1.00		13.00	1.00	2.00	17.00
6 - CyI		5.00	6.00	4.00	1.00	4.00	20.00
Total Person-Months	41.00	43.00	24.00	50.00	14.00	20.00	192.00

Table N. 7 Resource planning

RM ROADMAP

 rmroadmap.eu

 [@rmroadmap](https://twitter.com/rmroadmap)

 [linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap](https://www.linkedin.com/company/rmroadmap)

RM-ROADMAP project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under grant agreement number 101058475.